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Preliminary analysis of anemia in patients with active ulcerative colitis

Dr. Bijan Chandra Talukder *, **Dr. Xiaolan Zhang**, **Dr. Zheng Libo**

^{1,2}nd Hospital of Hebei Medical University, Department of Gastroenterology, China

***Corresponding author:**

dr.bijan07@gmail.com

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Abstract: Objective: The study objective is to investigate the degree and type of anemia in patients with active Ulcerative Colitis(UC). Methods: Retrospective investigation of clinical data of UC patients admitted to the department of gastroenterology of the second hospital of Hebei medical university from March 2014 to January 2018. 152 patients with ulcerative colitis and 44 controls were included. According to the Improved Mayo Scoring System and Montreal Classification, UC patients were further divided into different group. The currently used World Health Organization (WHO) definition of anemia applies also to patients with UC. Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software was used for statistical analysis. Result: The prevalence of anemia in the ulcerative colitis patients was higher as compared to the controls (58.6% vs 21.4%, $P < 0.01$). The prevalence of anemia in females in ulcerative colitis patients is higher as compared with the males ($P = 0.017$). But there is no different in ages. In the ulcerative colitis patients having anemia, 60 cases (67.42%) had mild anemia, 27 cases (30.34%) had moderate anemia and 2 cases (2.25%) had severe anemia. Microcytic anemia was 40.44% (36 cases), normocytic anemia was 44.94% and macrocytic anemia was 14.62%. In the UC patients, mean corpuscular volume (MCV) is smaller than that in the controls ($P = 0.014$) and red blood cell distribution width(RDW-CV) is bigger ($P = 0.036$). There was no significant difference between the range of UC and anemia. However, the more sever of UC, the more sever of anemia. Conclusion: 1. The prevalence of mild and moderate anemia in UC is common, particularly in female patients. 2. The prevalence of iron deficiency anemia and mix anemia were common.3. The more sever of UC, the more sever of anemia. 4. In the UC patients, MCV is smaller and RDW-CV is bigger as compared to controls.

Keywords: Ulcerative colitis, anemia, Clinical characteristics, severe of disease

Introduction

Ulcerative colitis (UC), one of the inflammatory bowel disease, is a chronic nonspecific easy-to-relapse inflammatory rectum and colon diseases, which main cause remains unknown. Diarrhea, abdominal pain and mucous bloody stool form are the main clinical manifestations of

this disease. With the increasing morbidity in the world, the more researches focus on its mechanism and complications prevention [1] .

Anemia is a common clinical symptom that the peripheral blood erythrocytes of human body is below the lower limit of the reference interval. According to World Health Organization criteria, anemia is defined as blood hemoglobin (Hb) concentration <130 g/L (<13 g/dL) or hematocrit (Hct) <39% in adult males; Hb <120 g/L (<12 g/dL) or Hct <37% in adult females. And it can inflict symptoms of fatigue, somnolence, dyspnea, headache and others [2] .

Collectively, anemia has a direct impact on the quality of life of UC patients. Anemia is one of common and serious complications of UC patients. Studies have shown that about 18% to 33.8% of UC patients have anemia and anemia are more common in women [3] . Anemia in UC patients may be related to multiple factors such as UC inflammation activity, chronic blood loss, malabsorption, dietary restrictions, immunosuppressant and other drugs applications, and hemolysis. Anemia can not only lead to a decrease in life quality of patients, but also prolong the hospital stay and increase the hospitalization rate [4] . Anemia includes iron deficiency anemia (IDA), anemia of chronic disease (ACD), megaloblastic anemia, hemolytic anemia and so on, among which IDA and ACD are the most common [5] .

Clinicians generally considered anemia as an inevitable concomitant symptom of IBD in the past, but in the recent years, attention has been paid to the injury caused by anemia in IBD patients. At the same time, rectifying anemia has been regarded as a principle for the treatment of IBD.

The aim of this study is to investigate the correlation between the degree and type of anemia and the severity and extent of active UC patients in China, and to analyze the peripheral blood red cell parameters and other relevant clinical data in UC patients in order to provide the basis for clinical precision treatment.

Treatment of iron-deficiency anemia in IBD is of significance because of the feasible outcomes on more than one organs and biological methods [6] . Those include cellular dysfunctions comprising impaired mitochondrial respiratory capacity and metabolic impairments that translate into precise organ dysfunctions, as an instance, in the important anxiety cases (e.g., impaired cognitive function, fatigue, stressed legs syndrome and despair), immune system (e.g., immune cell proliferation and differentiation and regulation of innate and adaptive immune responses), cardiorespiratory system (e.g., reduced exercise capacity, exertional dyspnea, tachycardia, palpitations, cardiac hypertrophy, systolic ejection murmur and risk of

cardiac failure), vascular device (e.g., hypothermia and pores and skin pallor), genital tract (e.g., lack of libido and menstrual problems) and gastrointestinal tract (e.g., anorexia, nausea and motility disorders [7-9] .

Recently, research have targeted on effectively screening and diagnosing identity of IDA in IBD. However, the management of this entity desires to be similarly highlighted. In truth, the position of IDA in IBD is not completely understood and present-day evidence frequently relies upon on decided on corporations of sufferers from tertiary care facilities [10] . Iron deficiency can be without problems corrected before progression into anemia, however, current evidence solely focuses on the ulcerative colitis (UC) associated with IDA [11] .

The gain of treating ID before the development of anemia remains unsure. But, iron supplementation must be taken into consideration in every IBD patient with IDA. [10] Therapy options for IDA fall especially into two categories, oral and intravenous (IV) iron formulations, and each treatment has benefits and downsides. [12] Consequently, the physicians need to undertake a treatment method on a patient-by patient foundation. Choosing the path of iron supplementation will depend upon whether symptoms are present, severity of the anemia, rate of Hb decline, and ability unfavorable effects of therapy [13] . Iron deficiency anemia persists in a vast share of patients with ulcerative colitis in remission and desires to be handled appropriately.

Materials and Methods

1. Research Object

1.1 In this study, 152 clinical data of UC patients hospitalized were selected from the Department of Gastroenterology, in the East Branch of the Second Hospital of Hebei Medical University from 2014.03 to 2018.01, and these data were selected according to the inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria.

1.2 Inclusion criteria: ①Ulcerative colitis patients were hospitalized between 2014.03-2018.01 in the East Branch of the Second hospital of Hebei Medical University; ②Ulcerative colitis patients contain blood routine examination; ③Clinical data is complete.

1.3 Exclusion criteria: ① patients without ulcerative colitis ② Ulcerative colitis patients with incomplete information; ③patients with diseases of the blood system; ④ patients younger than 14 years old ⑤ pregnant women.

1.4 Group: ①Control group: 44 patients of irritable bowel syndrome who were hospitalized at the same time; ②UC group: UC patients were divided into E1 (rectum) group, E2 (left colon)

group and E3(widely colon) group, according to the examination of colonoscopy; These UC patients were divided into mild activity group, moderate activity group, and severe activity group, according to Mayo score; These UC patients were also divided into 14-44 years old group, 45-65 years old group and older than 65 years old group, according to age; These UC patients were divided into macrocytic anemia group, normocytic anemia group and microcytic anemia group, according to anemia classification; Lastly, these UC patients were divided into mild group, moderate group, severe group and extremely severe group, according to anemia severity classification standards.

2. Research Methods

2.1 Medical records were collected including the ID, name, gender, age, endoscopic performance and blood routine examination, et al.

2.2 The diagnosis of ulcerative colitis is according to 2012 Guangzhou “The consensus of the diagnosis and treatment of inflammatory bowel disease”. Based on the exclusion of other diseases, diagnosis can be performed according to the following points [14] ①If a patient with typical clinical manifestation(persistent or recurrent diarrhea, mucus blood and pus with tenesmus, over the course of 4-6 weeks) is clinically suspected, the patient should be arranged for further examination; ②If a patient has both the following colonoscopy manifestations(electronic colonoscopy tips: Continuous diffuse lesions, mucosal congestion and edema, surface purulent secretions attached, vascular texture blurred, diffuse erosion or ulceration evident at lesions) and/or radiographic features, the patient can get a clinical diagnosis; ③If a patient gets the above-mentioned mucosal biopsy and (or) surgical specimen histopathological features, the patient can be confirmed (pathology: diffuse acute and chronic inflammatory cell infiltrates in the intrinsic membrane, with cryptitis, crypt abscess, crypt structure, size, irregular shape, branching, goblet cell reduction, etc) ; ④If the early onset of clinical manifestations, colonoscopy and biopsy histologic changes in atypical cases, they will not diagnosed with UC, and should be followed up.

2.3 Scopes of UC lesions are classified according to Montreal classification (Table 1). UC activity is judged according to the improved Mayo system score (Table 2).

2.4 In this study, the blood samples were tested by Unicel DXH 800 Coulter blood analyzer. According to the World Health Organization, anemia was defined adult males and females with blood hemoglobin concentration below 130 and 120 g/L, respectively.

3. Statistical Analysis

The measurement data of normal distribution are described by (mean±standard), and t test is used for comparison between groups. The number and percentage of counting cases are described. Chi square test is used for the two classifications, and trend chi square test is used for ordinal data. $P < 0.05$ showed that the difference was statistically significant. All statistical analyses were carried out using the social science statistical software package (SPSS.22).

RESULTS

1. Anemia in UC group and control group This study included 152 patients in the UC group, including 89 males and 63 females. The average age of UC group was 47.77 ± 15.25 years old, including 89 anemia patients (58.6%); In the control group, there were 44 cases, 23 males and 21 females, with an average age of 49.89 ± 11.80 years old, among which 9 patients (21.4%) were anemic. The incidence of anemia in UC group was higher than that in control group, and the difference between the two groups was statistically significant ($P < 0.001$) (Table 5).

2. Gender and age distribution of anemia group and non-anemia group in UC patients

There were 89 cases in anemia group, including 42 males and 47 females; 35 patients in age 14-44 years old, 42 patients in 45-65 years old, and 12 patients older than 65 years old. There were 63 cases in the non-anemia group, including 42 males and 21 females; 21 patients in age 14-44 years old, 32 patients in 45-65 years old, and 10 patients older than 65 years old. In the two groups, the incidence of anemia in women was significantly higher than that of male patients ($P=0.017$), but there was no significant difference in the incidence of anemia among three groups ($P=0.740$) (Table 6 and 7).

3. Correlation between the incidence of anemia in UC patients and the range of UC lesions.

There were 89 anemia patients in UC group, including 1 case of E1 type, 20 cases of E2 type, 68 cases of E3 type. There were 63 non-anemic patients among UC group, including 5 cases of E1 type, 17 cases of E2 type and 41 cases of E3 type. The difference between the three groups was statistically significant ($P=0.044$). Further comparisons between the two groups revealed significant differences between the E1 and E3 types ($P=0.027$). Type E3 patients with UC were more likely to have anemia. There was no significant difference between E1 and E2, E2 and E3 (Table 8).

4. Correlation between the incidence of anemia in UC patients and the severity of UC disease In anemia group, there were 9 patients with mild UC, 21 patients with moderate UC, 59 patients with

severe UC; and in non-anemia group, there were 10 patients with mild UC, 31 patients with moderate UC, and 22 patients with severe UC. The difference between the three groups was statistically significant ($P=0.001$). High incidence of anemia occurred in patients with severe UC than that in patients with mild and moderate patients ($P=0.032$; $P<0.001$), but there was no statistically significant difference between mild and moderate patients (Table 9).

5. The correlation between the type of anemia in UC and UC lesion. These UC patients included 36 cases of microcytic anemia, 40 cases of normocytic anemia, and 13 cases of macrocytic anemia. Microcytic anemia and normocytic anemia were the most common. Among them, E1 UC patients combined with microcytic anemia, normocytic anemia and macrocytic anemia were 0 cases, 0 cases, and 1 case. E2 UC patients combined with the three types anemia were 6 cases, 11 cases and 3 cases, respectively, and E3 UC patients were 30 cases, 29 cases and 9 cases, respectively. There was no significant difference between the groups ($P>0.05$) (Table 10).

6. Correlation analysis between the degree of anemia in UC patients and the extent of UC lesions. Among the UC patients with mild anemia, there were 1 case of E1 type, 16 cases of E2 type and 43 cases of E3 type. Among moderate anemic UC patients, there were 0 case of E1 type, 4 cases of E2 type, 23 cases of E3 type. Among the UC patients with severe anemia, there were 0 case of E1 type, 0 cases of E2 type, 2 cases of E3 type. The comparison between groups showed that the severity of anemia was positively correlated with the extent of UC lesions ($P=0.038$) (Table 11).

7. Correlation analysis of anemia and UC severity in UC patients. Among mild anemia patients, there were 8 cases of mild UC, 16 cases of moderate UC, and 36 cases of severe UC. Among moderate anemia patients, 0 case were mild UC, 6 cases were moderate UC, 21 cases were severe UC; among the patients with severe anemia, there were 0 cases of mild UC, 0 cases of moderate UC, and 2 cases of severe UC. There was no significant correlation between the degree of anemia and the severity of UC in each group (Table 12).

8. The relationship between the type of anemia and the degree of UC in patients with UC. Among the patients with microcytic anemia, there were 1 case of mild UC, 11 cases of moderate UC, and 24 cases of severe UC; among the patients with normocytic anemia, 8 cases were mild UC patients, 9 cases were moderate UC, 23 cases were severe UC. Among patients with macrocytic anemia, there were 0 mild UC patients, 1 moderate patient, and 12 severe patients. The difference between the groups was statistically significant ($P=0.027$). Further comparisons

between the two groups revealed that there was a statistically significant difference between normocytic anemia and macrocytic anemia in severe UC patients (P=0.022), with a higher incidence of normocytic anemia (Table 13).

9. Red blood cell related indicators of anemia patients in UC group and control group.

There was a significant difference in hemoglobin(HGB), Mean corpuscular volume(MCV), Red Blood Cell Distribution Width RDW-CV in UC patients with anemia and control groups with anemia (P=0.017; P=0.014; P=0.036). There was no significant difference between the two groups in red blood cells (RBC), Mean corpuscular hemoglobin(MCH), Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration(MCHC), and RDW-SD (Table 14).

Tables

Table 1 Distribution of UC

Term	Distribution	Description
E1	Proctitis	Involvement limited to the rectum [i.e. proximal extent of inflammation is distal to the recto-sigmoid junction]
E2	Left-sided	Involvement limited to the proportion of the colon distal to the splenic flexure [analogous to 'distal' colitis]
E3	Extensive	Involvement extends proximal to the splenic flexure, including pan-colitis

Table 2 Mayo score for ulcerative colitis

Mayo index	0	1	2	3
Stool frequency	Normal	1-2/day > normal	3-4/day > normal	5/day > normal
Rectal bleeding Mucosa	None Normal	Streaks Mild friability	Obvious Moderate friability	Mostly blood Spontaneous bleeding
Physician's global assessment	Normal	Mild	Moderate	Severe

Table 3 Anemia severity classification standards

Hb	<30g/L	30-59g/L	60-90g/L	>90g/L
Severity of anemia	Extremely severe	Severe	Moderate	Mild

Table 4 Anemia classification

Type	MCV(fl)	Red blood cell volume	MCH(pg)	MCHC(%)
macrocytic anemia	>100	Small	>34	32~35
normocytic anemia	80~100	Normal	27~34	32~35
microcytic anemia	<80	Large	<27	<32

Table 5 Incidence of anemia in UC group and control group

	UC group	Control	X ²	OR	P
Anemia	89 (58.6%)	9 (21.4%)	18.143	5.18	0.000
Non-anemia	63 (41.4%)	33 (78.6%)			

Table 6 Anemia in UC patients and anemia distribution in different sexes

	UC group		X ²	OR	P
	Anemia	Non-anemia			
Male	42 (50%)	42 (50%)	5.659	0.447	0.017
Female	47 (69.1%)	21 (30.9%)			

Table 7 The distribution of UC patients with anemia at different age stages

Age	UC group		X ²	P
	Anemia	Non-anemia		
14-44	35 (39.3%)	21 (33.3%)	0.603	0.74
45-65	42 (47.2%)	32 (50.8%)		
>65	12 (13.5%)	10 (15.9%)		

Table 8 The distribution of anemia in different lesions of UC

Disease area	UC group		X ²	P
	Anemia	Non-anemia		
E1	1 (1.1%)	5 (7.9%)	4.054	0.044
E2	20 (22.5%)	17 (27%)		
E3	68 (76.4%)	41 (65.1%)		

Table 9 The distribution of anemia in different lesions of UC

Disease degree	UC group		X ²	P
	Anemia	Non-anemia		
Mild	9 (10.1%)	10 (15.9%)	14.86	0.001
Moderate	21 (23.6%)	31 (49.2%)		
Severe	59 (66.3%)	22 (34.9%)		

Table 10 The distribution of anemia in different lesions of UC

Degree of anemia	Disease degree		
	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Mild	8	16	36
Moderate	0	6	21
Severe	0	0	2

Table 11 The distribution of anemia in different lesions of UC

Degree of anemia	UC lesions		
	E1	E2	E3
Mild	1	16	43
Moderate	0	4	23
Severe	0	0	2

Table 12 The distribution of anemia in different lesions of UC

Anemia type	Degree of UC			X ²	P
	Mild	Moderate	Severe		
normocytic anemia	8 (88.9%)	9 (42.9%)	23 (39%)	7.286	0.007
microcytic anemia	1 (11.1%)	11 (52.4%)	24 (40.7%)		
macrocytic anemia	0	1 (4.8%)	12 (20.3%)		

Table 13 The distribution of anemia in different lesions of UC

Anemia type	UC lesions			X ²	P
	E1	E2	E3		
normocytic anemia	0	11 (55%)	29 (42.6%)	0.048	0.826
microcytic anemia	0	6 (30%)	30 (44.1%)		
macrocytic anemia	1 (100%)	3 (15%)	9 (13.2%)		

Table 14 Description and comparison of red blood cell related indicators

Detection Indicator	Control (anemia)	UCgroup (anemia)	P
RBC	3.91±0.26	3.79±0.54	0.469
HGB	114.45±4.34	99.19±20.74	0.017
MCV	90.33±4.24	83.69±8.87	0.014
MCH	29.30±1.50	27.89±9.95	0.642
MCHC	324.45±8.23	316.21±20.92	0.200
RDW-SD	42.85±4.57	49.72±4.16	0.587
RDW-CV	13.09±0.98	15.11±3.12	0.036

Discussion

Ulcerative colitis is a chronic, or long lasting, disease that causes inflammation irritation or swelling and sores called ulcers on the inner lining of the large intestine. Ulcerative colitis is a chronic inflammatory disease of the gastrointestinal (GI) tract, called inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). [4]. Anemia in ulcerative colitis has been attributed to continual blood loss, anemia of chronic disease, folate deficiency due to sulfasalazine therapy or azathioprine prompted. Anemia is a frequent complication in patients with ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease, with

reported rates varying between 30% and 50% [15]. Anemia can result in signs like continual fatigue impairing the best of lifestyles [16].

The main types of anemia in IBD patients are iron deficiency anemia and inflammatory anemia or anemia of chronic disease. As many reports have focused at the vital trouble of anemia in IBD patients. Subsequently evolved the first simple tips for prognosis and management of iron-deficiency anemia in IBD patients so that it will improve patients care and fine of existence [17]. Iron enact a key part of hemoglobin in erythrocytes and of myoglobin in muscle groups, which in mixture consist of about two-thirds of the general body iron [18]. Further, iron is important to an intensive range of natural approaches [19]. The common individual harbors more than 3-4 g of iron, that's balanced between physiologic iron loss and dietary uptake [18]. About 20–25 mg of iron is needed day by day for the synthesis of heme. Therefore about 1-2 mg originates from nutritional consumption and the remainder is received by using recycling of iron from senescent erythrocytes by way of the usage of macrophages [20].

Dietary iron is available in forms: heme and non-heme-certain iron. Within heme, iron is complexed as ferrous iron (Fe^{2+}) to the protoporphyrin ring, this is ample in animal food merchandise consisting of meat, hen and seafood [21]. Most dietary iron is vast as nonheme iron (Fe^{3+} or ferric iron) and is located in ingredients of vegetable starting place (e.g., Nuts, beans, vegetables and fortified grain products). Heme iron is believed to represent 10-15% of typical iron intake in meat-ingesting populations but due to its higher bioavailability (anticipated absorption fee of 15–35%) than nonheme iron(5-15%), it money owed for extra than 30% of the whole absorbed iron [22].

Systemically by way of several mechanisms is regulated of frame iron homeostasis, amongst that is the pivotal interaction of the liver-derived peptide hormone hepcidin with the principal cellular iron exporter ferroprotein [23]. Ferroprotein is found basically on intestinal epithelium (mostly in the duodenum), macrophages and hepatocytes, which constitute the essential cellular iron stores. Ferroprotein accordingly allows the delivery of iron from cells into the circulation to maintain adequate systemic iron levels [24]. Focused on of ferroprotein by using hepcidin consequences in ferroprotein internalization, degradation and blockage of cell iron egress into the serum, for this reason resulting in a discounted availability of iron for erythroid progenitor cells. Synthesis and launch of hepcidin and therefore cell accumulation of iron and improvement of a low serum iron concentration, are precipitated by each an excessive awareness

of iron in the liver and plasma and by inflammatory cytokines including IL-1 (IL: interleukin) and IL-6 [25]. Cytokine-pushed induction of hepcidin expression and the direct results of cytokines on iron trafficking in macrophages and duodenal enterocytes play a decisive function inside the improvement of ACD or anemia of infection by means of using preserving iron in the reticuloendothelial device and blocking off iron absorption [26], causing an iron-limited erythropoiesis. For that reason, anemia of persistent disorder (ACD) is extra normal in patients with superior disease and in those responding poorly to remedy. In addition, cytokines and chemokines further make a contribution to anemia by way of way of negatively influencing the organic activity of erythropoietin, through inhibiting the proliferation and differentiation of erythroid progenitor cells and via reducing the circulatory 1/2-existence of erythrocytes [27]. However, sufferers with flaring IBD enjoy blood loss due to intestinal mucosal bleeding, which regularly motives proper iron deficiency collectively with inflammatory anemia (reflected via low to everyday ferritin degrees).

The WHO defines anemia as a stage of Hb below 13.0 g/dL in male adults, below 12.0 g/dL in woman adults who aren't pregnant, and beneath 11.0 g/dL in pregnant women tiers can also range throughout age and race, so care need to be taken, especially within the interpretation of borderline values [28].

Moreover, smokers and population of higher altitudes may additionally have higher baseline Hb levels, and participation in persistence sports might also regulate Hb stages. The mean corpuscular Hb and mean corpuscular volume distinguish macrocytic anemia from iron deficiency anemia, that's hypochromic and commonly microcytic [29]. Deficiencies of a couple of nutrients (e.g. malabsorption) or the usage of thiopurine medications (e.g. azathioprine in IBD) can result in a combination of iron deficiency anemia and macrocytosis, with resultant normocytic anemia. In this example, a huge purple cellular distribution width aids identity of the iron deficiency element [30]. In addition parameters to diagnose iron deficiency are the transferrin saturation (TfS), which reflects the iron available for erythropoiesis, and the serum degree of ferritin, an iron storage protein [31]. If the analysis remains doubtful, the soluble transferrin receptor (sTfR) and sTfR/log ferritin index (<1) may be used to differentiate between iron deficiency anemia and ACD due to the fact the sTfR is improved best in iron deficiency anemia [32, 33]. Inflammatory bowel diseases patients should have hemoglobin, ferritin, and C-reactive protein (CRP) measured at least each 6 to 12 months when in remission or with slight disease, and

each 3 months while moderate to excessive relapse takes place [34] . A latest have a look at in veterans observed that greater than a third of anemic ulcerative colitis patients had been no longer tested for iron deficiency and almost 1/4 of the patients with iron deficiency anemia had been not handled with iron alternative therapy [35] .

The intention of anemia therapy in IBD is to improve quality of lifestyles, decrease the frequency and length of health center admissions, and avoid blood transfusions. Additionally, it is done with the aid of normalizing hemoglobin, ferritin, and TfS degrees [34] .

The usual treatment of iron IDA with oral iron has relevant obstacles in IBD patients. Intestinal iron absorption is confined. The most rate of absorption of 100 mg of oral iron is 20% to 25% and is reached simplest inside the overdue stage of iron deficiency. Latent iron deficiency and iron deficiency anemia correspond to mean absorption rates of 10% and 13%, respectively, while healthy males absorb 5% and healthy females 5.6%. Iron that stays inside the intestinal lumen may additionally purpose mucosal harm [7, 36] . The bivalent iron salts ferrous fumarate, ferrous sulfate, and ferrous gluconate are the maximum frequently used oral preparations and are preferred over ferric iron arrangements [37] . The endorsed every day dose for adults with id is 100–200 mg of elemental iron daily, while in youngsters, doses of 3 to 6 mg/kg of body weight of a liquid practice are recommended [12, 38] . For the treatment of IDA, cutting-edge tips propose the dose of 60–120 mg of elemental iron in line with day for a minimal length of 3 months in youth and adults, inclusive of pregnant women [39, 40] . The addition of diet C with oral iron therapy may additionally enhance absorption. A length of 3 to 6 months of treatment is required to normalize serum ferritin ranges and refill iron stores [12] . Current data comparing ferrous sulfate preparations with ferric iron polymaltose complex arrangements display that the previous continue to be the set up and general therapy of identity, no matter the indication, given their proper bioavailability, efficacy, and suitable tolerability, as established in numerous huge medical studies [41, 42] . A novel oral iron compound referred to as ferric maltol, which was traditionally used as a meals additive is now recommended as an oral treatment alternative in patients with IBD. In comparison to the ferrous formulations, this compound is assumed to permit greater efficient uptake of elemental iron into enterocytes at the side of a safer gastrointestinal profile [43] . In a phase III scientific trial in which sufferers with IBD who have been known to be illiberal or unresponsive to the ferrous iron arrangements were handled for 12 weeks with ferric maltol, a widespread improvement in Hb concentration through 2.25 g/dL become discovered inside

the ferric maltol-dealt with sufferers (as opposed to placebo) [43]. Any other section III double-blinded extension examine changed into performed in 2016 to evaluate the efficacy and protection of ferric maltol in patients with IBD who did not reap normalization of Hb degrees after remedy with oral ferrous treatments around 80% of members executed ordinary Hb levels and accelerated iron stores the use of ferric maltol, which was also well tolerated [44]. This is taken into consideration a clinically significant exchange based totally on modern-day tips for the management of IDA in IBD [43].

Intravenous iron is greater effective, shows a faster reaction, and is higher tolerated than oral iron. As a consequence, intravenous iron preparations are desired inside the correction of IBD-related anemia and were encouraged also in preceding international hints [13]. Intravenous iron is safe, effective, and properly tolerated each in the correction of IDA and renovation of iron stores in sufferers with IBD [45].

The advantage of using IV iron is that it bypasses gastrointestinal absorption, which is known to be variable in IBD patients. IV iron therapy is commonly encouraged in instances of unequivocal responses to oral iron (Hb boom <50–100 g/L in 2 weeks), patient noncompliance, intolerance to oral iron due to GI facet effects, and inside the event of extreme, advanced or innovative anemia. In sufferers with IBD, intravenously administered iron does now not worsen disorderactivity [46, 47]. It's miles vital to degree the Hb ranges weeks after IV iron treatment initiation in symptomatic sufferers and after 4 weeks in asymptomatic sufferers, and the treatment is considered successful if the Hb attention increases with the aid of at the least 2 g/dL or reaches everyday within 4 weeks of remedy initiation [9]. Six main sorts of IV iron are available: iron sucrose, ferric gluconate, ferric carboxymaltose, iron isomaltoside-1000, ferumoxytol, and iron dextran (low-molecular-weight forms) [48]. There was an awful lot debate on whether or not low- or excessive-dose IV iron is extra green in hastily replenishing iron stores. Gisbertet al. Reported a 77% reaction charge in IBD patients taking iron sucrose 2 × 200 mg/week and Kulnigget al. Replicated this equal reaction price of 77% in IBD sufferers taking ferric carboxymaltose at a maximum dose of one thousand mg iron in keeping with infusion at 1-week intervals [49, 50]. Ferric carboxymaltose changed into discovered to be superior to iron sucrose in phrases of efficacy however side results such as rash, dermatitis, and pruritus were greater present inside the former than the latter organization. Infusion-web site reactions had been more prominent inside

the iron sucrose infusion, primarily due to the alkaline pH of the solution and the better range of infusions.

In a few patients, treatment of the underlying IBD along with iron, folic acid, and diet B12 supplementation is not enough to efficaciously accurate anemia [9]. In such cases, treatment with erythropoietin stimulating agents (ESAs), have to be taken into consideration. ESAs are utilized in patients whose anemia is refractory to IV therapy and are not considered as a primary-line treatment. Furthermore, these agents also are recommended while immunosuppressive therapy has no longer suppressed infection, and for sufferers requiring blood transfusions [51].

Conclusion

Anemia was seen in more than half of patients with ulcerative colitis in clinical remission, iron deficiency being the most common cause. In clinical practice, most UC patients with anemia received oral iron even though this administration route may aggravate the disease, and despite international guidelines recommending intravenous administration as the preferred route. The high frequency of ID suggests insufficient monitoring of iron status in UC patients. There is a need to increase awareness and implementation of international guidelines on iron supplementation in patients with IBD. Therefore, one purpose within the care of IBD especially ulcerative colitis patients is to heighten the awareness of the common co prognosis of anemia leading to affordable diagnostic method and powerful therapy to growth patients' nice of existence. Patients should be identified and can be screened by an easily available investigation like a hemogram and their iron, vitamin B12 and folate deficiency can be corrected in a cost-effective manner. Anemia persists in a significant proportion of patients with active ulcerative colitis and needs to be treated appropriately. Iron deficiency anemia persists in a vast share of patients with ulcerative colitis in remission and desires to be handled appropriately.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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